

This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Date	February 28 – March 1, 2018
Venue	Day 1; Globus hotel, Day 2; ISS, Rome, Italy
Meeting	NOVA first annual meeting (kick-off)
Room	Day 1; Ping, Day 2; Aula Marotta + other rooms

Meeting Minutes

Discussed topics

DAY 1

1. Welcome

The project coordinator *Jenny Frössling* welcomed participants and *Umberto Agrimi*, the head of the food safety department at ISS, the institution kindly hosting the meeting, opened the meeting giving a short presentation on the ISS (Italian National Institute of Health). *Gaia Scavia* overviewed the practical information regarding the location and meeting arrangements.

2. Presentation round

As an ice-breaker, participants were given a chance to get to know each other in pairs, and present each other to the group.

3. Introduction of EJP and NOVA, Jenny Frössling

Jenny passed on general information about the overall EJP program, received in previous presentations from the EJP to project coordinators. She also reviewed the overall NOVA structure and plan.

4. WP2 Analysis of food purchase data, Steen Ethelberg

Steen opened with a presentation on the motivation for this WP. He presented an outbreak investigation case in which the food purchase data solved the source investigation. He also reviewed the insertion of WP2 in the NOVA structure, and the text and tasks for this WP in the project description.

All WPs were asked to highlight the *novel* aspects of their plan, which in this case is clear, since this type of data has never before been used systematically for surveillance.

5. WP3 Syndromic surveillance, Adeline Huneau

Adeline quickly reviewed the concept of syndromic surveillance, and the goal of WP3 as identifying how could syndromic surveillance be a valuable add-on to the current/future surveillance of foodborne zoonoses. Adeline also highlighted a strong synergy with WP1, the main interests in Salmonella and AMR, and the expected output as a proof of concept. The sources of data that will be investigated to cover the foodborne field were described as primary production, processing/retail and consumption. This elicited a discussion on the types of courses and the viability of accessing data in all 3 groups in all countries. Data examples were listed, which are already available, although the possibility to get all 3 categories of data is not certain at the moment (it is desirable). It was highlighted the task of multivariate analysis, which will serve as a proof of concept to the integration of data across all 3 categories, even if we only have access to data in a couple of categories, but maybe different categories in different countries. Not all data will fit the traditional idea of “syndromic”, and the integrated analysis of med-vet-food is the highlighted novel aspect of this WP.

It was suggested (Eric Evers) that a risk assessment approach may be more useful than a multivariate analysis approach to addressing the multitude of data sources and need to integrate evidence.

The issue of overlap with other projects was raised, but Jenny pointed out that we have a specific point in the agenda to discuss this issue tomorrow. Steen suggested that we should keep a list of which other projects people are involved in. A list was circulated in the meeting.

6. WP4 Spatial risk mapping, Ana de la Torre

Ana reviewed the WP structure – partners, the three listed tasks, the task leaders and deliverables. Ana also highlighted the aspects of other WPs that connect with WP4, and which it is important to review together. Ana and Julio Alvarez Sanchez described some of the data that will be available in Spain soon, but some details of the plan will only become clearer once they have access to the data.

It was also highlighted that the specific case of Salmonella in Spain should serve only as a case study, but the WP needs to be generalized as a novel methodology that can be applied to other pathogens and countries.

7. WP1 Food chain surveillance mapping, Valérie De Waele

Valerie reviewed the WP structure, with two main tasks (terminology and mapping) and the leaders. It was highlighted that all institutions involved were assigned to WP1 and are expected to contribute. Existing resources on terminology (RISKSUR project, ICAHS workshop, EFSA standards) were listed, and these resources need now to be applied to the food chain surveillance. Overlaps with ongoing projects (ORION in particular) were highlighted and the need to work together to avoid work duplication. A business process model to be adopted to surveillance by the ORION project was presented (Generic Statistical

Business Process Model – GSBPM). Valerie also raised the question of whether other ongoing projects in the participating countries are already doing some of the work of mapping the surveillance activities.

During the discussions about how the tasks should be tackled, Jenny and Solveig highlighted that the initial plan when this WP was planned was quite a simple one, to describe surveillance across the food chain, focusing on specific case examples, and at every step describe data, activities, main hurdles, etc. Fernanda complemented that this is in line with the learned lessons from RISKSUR, and helps keep a complementary, but not overlapping approach to ORION, where a more detailed, generic, statistical business process model will be constructed focusing on meta data in particular.

In the interest of time we moved on, but it was agreed that this is an important point and should be revisited tomorrow.

8. WP5 Evaluation of surveillance programs and cost efficiency, Håkan Vigre

Håkan reviewed the structure of this WP which he described as computer intensive and strongly relying on mathematical modeling. All WP participants have experience with disease modeling. In this WP models will be adapted to be able to assess the effect of surveillance design (the apparent reality is a reflection of how we sample the population through surveillance). Håkan listed the challenges to achieve this vision, including access to data and collaboration on coding.

Challenges were highlighted, but an important opportunity is the amount of data regarding the population available in Denmark – this will allow the representation of the “reality” to be very precise.

DAY 2

1. Welcome to the second day

The group gathered at ISS, to then break out into discussion groups for the individual WPs. Discussions within each WP are documented by the leaders and summarized below.

2. Summary of WP discussions

WP2: reviewed which data each partner has. Data will not be shared, but a tool may be shared for analysis across the institutions.

WP3: agreed on a task plan for the first year and shared to-dos.

WP4: a timeline and road-map were delineated for the first year. Information about the available data sources in each country were gathered, in order to identify the common points.

WP5: discussions were motivated by a few driving questions that inform how surveillance can be measured: What is the effect of surveillance? What kind of answers to the stakeholders need? What models already exist?

WP1: Discussed the need for communication within NOVA, and other projects in EJP, in particular ORION and COHESIVE. The group is of the opinion that it should be kept simple.

3. Joint discussion of WP1

Steen posted the question – what is the main goal in the WP? Fernanda suggested that we should try to keep to practical and applied to specific examples. On the subject of synergies with other projects, she suggested that ORION seems to be focusing on general frameworks,

so we are “safe” in not replicating work if we focus on describing specific surveillance practices. Gaia remarked that a general framework already exists, in the form of EU legislation. She also suggested that we should be careful with interviewing member states, and they may have given the same information many time for different projects. Our work needs to keep in line with the EU framework and existing outcomes of projects and EFSA work.

Jenny highlighted that we should not be focusing only on data, and reminded that when the application was written the thought for WP1 was to describe surveillance steps, focusing not only on data but also on people, attitudes, barriers, etc. To carry out a descriptive analysis and qualitative evaluation of what does the food chain look like, what works, who is involved, etc.

The suggested concrete goal is then to identify opportunities for *One Health* surveillance, and to identify the points where (and how) we could apply the tools developed within each WP.

It was also suggested to focus on a specific case study, and Salmonella emerged as the best candidate. It would give an opportunity to highlight the differences among the countries, even if they are following the same EU framework. Countries can apply it to more pathogens/hazards if they have the interest – AMR and Campylobacter came up. Jenny highlighted that once we come up with a description framework for Salmonella, we can see if it can be applicable to carry out a descriptive analysis of other goals.

Gaia pointed out that we should strive to give feedback to the commission about what works, what could be alternatives, how things could be improved. The tools we are developing are not pathogen specific, but a case study on WP1 could help identify these points.

How should we then go about getting this WP started - a small group should start sketching the **food chain** and the surveillance opportunities within it, for the specific Salmonella case, and circulate for all countries to contribute to this general sketch. Based on that, the same small group should design a questionnaire and pilot it. As every institution is participating in this WP, each institution could then apply the questionnaire in their country. This will probably be an iterative process, where the results of the first round of questionnaire may raise questions that will be discussed in interviews with key people.

Luigi: What is done versus what we would like to do – the WP1 identify gaps as well, and the future comes into the tools developed by each WP.

Extend the salmonella case to AMR?

Estelle: AMR. Salmonella as the “mandatory” case to compare across countries, but individual countries can apply to more if they have the interest.

Jenny: it will be easier to see whether we can generalize to others, once we see the questionnaire we end up with.

4. Extra agenda point: PhD opportunities within the NOVA

The group asked to discuss the PhD opportunities that will be offered through EJP’s WP6, as presented by Roberto La Ragione during the EJP kick-off in Paris. Jenny showed Roberto’s power point presentation. There will be opportunities to 12 PhD positions to be created within the EP framework – the proposed deadline was March 12th, and it is now extended until April (the exact date is not known by Jenny – interested people can contact Roberto). A link to existing EJP research projects is encouraged but not required, but the project should link at least 2 EJP partners. Positions are 3-4 years. Ana said that she thinks there may be an opportunity to apply for a PhD student that could be linked to NOVA in her institute.

5. Project management

Fernanda presented a SharePoint website which could give us the opportunity to have a platform for: creating email distribution lists; create a task planner; have a shared calendar; and share files. The solution SVA can offer to users outside the institution will only be available after the end of March (due to licensing issues). Since the EJP coordination has also mentioned providing task planning tools by March, we will have to wait a bit until setting up any project management tool. Armin pointed out that BfR does not allow them to host data in any Microsoft server, so this will have to be considered.

6. Overlap and collaboration with other projects

Armin highlighted the upcoming kick-off workshops: COHESIVE 28-29 March, ORION 18-20th of April.

Fernanda pointed out that NOVA is thinking of the mapping exercise as a way to draw the food chain and the opportunities for surveillance there, which ORION is more focusing on the surveillance design and the steps of surveillance data processing.

Jenny also pointed out a key point of differentiation, which is the research focus of NOVA, versus the integrative focus of ORION and COHESIVE. She recommends that we should always consider what is the research question for each WP.

The meeting was closed on time at 3pm, with a round of applause to thank Gaia for the local arrangements.

List of documents attached to the minutes:

- Final agenda
- Registration form
- List of participants
- Participants' signatures